

Research paper

Increasing groundwater storage and maintaining irrigation through managed aquifer recharge

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HIGHLIGHTS

- First evaluation in Europe of a long-term, large-scale managed aquifer recharge (MAR) scheme in the agricultural context.
- MAR provides approximately 25% of local agricultural groundwater demand.
- MAR contributes to increasing groundwater levels in Los Arenales groundwater body at a rate of ~ 0.4 m/year.
- Irrigation communities formed to exploit MAR help to improving water governance and decreasing groundwater demand.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Managed aquifer recharge (MAR)
Hydrogeology
Trend analysis
Field significance
Irrigation

ABSTRACT

Aquifers providing groundwater for agriculture are in many cases unsustainably managed, resulting in environmental degradation and socioeconomic impacts. In this context, strategies that contribute to recovering groundwater reserves and satisfactorily maintaining irrigation are essential. Los Arenales Aquifer (Spain) experienced a dramatic decline in groundwater level in the last quarter of the 20th century due to intensive agricultural abstractions. We assess whether this aquifer has recovered in recent years and the potential contribution of managed aquifer recharge (MAR). We evaluate the significance of groundwater level trends and their magnitude through the (regional) Mann-Kendall test and the Theil-Sen estimator. We also calculate the average groundwater level and explore factors that could influence the observed trends, such as MAR, land use, agricultural water demand, and water management measures. We also contrast two groundwater management regions located within Los Arenales Aquifer, namely Los Arenales (LA), which has implemented MAR, and Medina del Campo (MC), to obtain further insight into groundwater development. The hydro statistical analyses reveal a continuous drop in groundwater levels of about -1.3 m/year in LA between 1985 and 2001, followed by a consistent recovery. In MC, groundwater levels decrease in two out of three analysis periods. We show that MAR is spatially and temporally correlated with increasing groundwater level trends. Land use, agricultural

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gsd.2022.100842>

Received 24 June 2022; Received in revised form 23 August 2022; Accepted 6 September 2022

Available online 10 September 2022

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water demand, and water management measures have remained similar throughout the analysis period or have a limited impact on groundwater use. Furthermore, the only significant water management measure MC differs from LA is MAR. These pieces of evidence point to MAR as the primary mechanism for replenishing Los Arenales Aquifer, showing the potential of this tool to recover stressed aquifers and sustain irrigation in the area and beyond.

1. Introduction

Groundwater is vital globally. It meets the water needs of around two billion people (Gleeson et al., 2012) and contributes to irrigating more than 43% of the global irrigated land, a percentage that is expected to increase in the future (Hanjra and Qureshi, 2010). However, groundwater's low visibility has resulted in large overdrafts in many regions, leading to unsustainable groundwater development and hence aquifer overexploitation (Alley, 2002; Custodio, 2002; Famiglietti, 2014; Gleeson et al., 2012; Konikow and Kendy, 2005). This problem is particularly tangible in some aquifers that sustain large-scale agriculture, such as the Upper Ganges (India-Pakistan), the North Arabian (Saudi Arabia), the Central Valley (USA), and the Canning basin (Australia) (Famiglietti, 2014; Gleeson et al., 2012).

In Spain, groundwater irrigation represents 27% of the 33,000 km² of total irrigated land and offers a much higher socioeconomic efficiency (in terms of €/m³ and jobs/m³) than supply-based surface water irrigation (Aldaya et al., 2010; Garrido et al., 2006). Many aquifers in Spain are considered overexploited or highly stressed due to unsustainable irrigation (Llamas et al., 2015; Rupérez-Moreno et al., 2017; Van Loon and Van Lanen, 2013). One significant example of these aquifers is Los Arenales, located on the Spanish side of the Douro River basin. Throughout the second half of the XX century, this region witnessed a rapid increase in groundwater-based irrigation. State supports such as low-interest loans, tax exemptions, and technological innovations that made it possible to extract water from greater depths attracted agricultural entrepreneurs (Llamas et al., 2015; Baraja Rodríguez, 2012). This socioeconomic context resulted in extensive unregulated groundwater exploitation, which was reflected in widespread drawdowns throughout Los Arenales, where groundwater levels dropped by up to 27 m between 1972 and 2002 (Fernández-Escalante et al., 2016). This evident crisis and the imminent implementation of the Water Framework Directive (WFD) (European Parliament and Council of the European Union, 2000) forced the local water management authorities and farmers to change their view on water resources toward sustainability (Baraja Rodríguez, 2012; Llamas and Garrido, 2007; Soto-García et al., 2013). Consequently, farmers in Los Arenales promoted the construction of managed aquifer recharge (MAR) systems to maintain groundwater irrigation, resulting in El Carracillo, Santiuste, and Pedrajas-Alcazarén MAR sites in 2002, 2003, and 2012 (Fernández-Escalante et al., 2016; MAPA, 1998).

MAR is a technique to recharge and store water in aquifers intentionally. The additional water stored can be used for various purposes (Dillon, 2009a; 2019) and can contribute to tackling a variety of water-related issues, such as saltwater intrusion (Werner and Simmons, 2009), some of the effects of climate change (Fernández-Escalante et al., 2019b), and groundwater contamination (Scanlon et al., 2005), among others.

Some studies have evaluated the regional effect of MAR systems on aquifers stressed by agriculture. Most of these studies show that MAR is significant to a local extent with a net depletion of storage at the regional level. Furthermore, they highlight that MAR is not a panacea and requires additional strategies (e.g. surface and groundwater conjunctive use and demand control) to improve the quantity of groundwater in overexploited aquifers effectively (Dillon et al., 2009b; Thomas and Famiglietti, 2015; Scanlon et al., 2016; Wendt et al., 2020). However, some authors report a net positive effect of implementing MAR (Jadhav et al., 2021; Bachtouli and Comte, 2019).

Several studies have explored the effect of the MAR sites on Los Arenales Aquifer. These studies have focused on hydrogeological (CONAMA, 2019), socioeconomic (Fernández-Escalante et al., 2016), governance (Fernández-Escalante and López-Gunn, 2021), climate change (Fernández-Escalante et al., 2019b; Henao Casas et al., 2022), and technical (Fernández-Escalante and Prieto Leache, 2013; Fernández-Escalante and San Sebastian Sauto, 2019a; MARSOL, 2015) aspects. However, none of them has analysed the evolution of groundwater levels and water use dynamics on a regional scale.

The main goal of the present study is to determine whether Los Arenales Aquifer has recovered in recent years and, if so, to elucidate the contribution of MAR. Our approach involves collecting evidence using different statistical methods and evaluating socioeconomic dynamics that might affect groundwater development. We analyse local and regional groundwater level trends and average groundwater levels. We also conduct analyses of agricultural water demand, land use and cropping patterns, and water management measures. Additionally, we contrast two groundwater management regions that are part of Los Arenales Aquifer and underwent a similar storage depletion in the second half of the XX century. Still, they seem to have evolved significantly differently in the last decade. This study is one of the few to evaluate the effect of large-scale operational MAR systems. Furthermore, to the best of our knowledge, a comprehensive evaluation involving long-term groundwater data monitoring and MAR in the agricultural context has only been carried out in the Central Valley aquifer (Wendt et al., 2020) and the coastal Korba aquifer, Tunisia (Bachtouli and Comte, 2019). Therefore, this study constitutes the first assessment in Europe. It also presents a comprehensive approach to assessing the impact of water management measures in areas with hydrogeological and socioeconomic complexity (in this case, heterogeneity and compartmentalisation of the aquifer systems and the lack of long-term agricultural and groundwater abstraction data) that represent large uncertainties for numerical models, precluding their use.

2. Methodology

2.1. Case study background

The study area is located in the autonomous community of Castile and Leon (94,224 km²), central Spain. It extends over a flat area on the central plateau of the Douro River basin (Fig. 1). The region's climate is continental Mediterranean and is characterised by long cold winters (average temperature about 3–6 °C) and short, mild summers (average temperature about 19–22 °C) (Segovia-Cardozo et al., 2019). Average precipitation and evapotranspiration are, respectively, 395 mm and 1129. Most of the precipitation occurs between October and May.

Agriculture in the region is the primary land use and occupies ~70% of the land. Irrigation represents about 25% of total agricultural land and consumes ~98% of total groundwater abstraction. Cereals are the main crops covering about 55% of the total agricultural land and representing nearly 30% of the irrigated land (Rivas-Tabares et al., 2019). Wheat and barley predominate in the region. Other representative crops are sugar beets and sunflowers.

In hydrogeological terms, Los Arenales Aquifer entails two main systems. The first system comprises phreatic aquifers in shallow-thickness quaternary deposits (~10 m). The second system involves lenticular and elongated bodies of sand and gravel embedded in an impermeable to semipermeable matrix of silt, clay and, to a minor

extent, gypsum (Antón et al., 2012; Fernández-Escalante et al., 2016; Navarro Alvargonzález et al., 1993). This system is part of the Paleogene-Neogene fill of the Douro River basin and reaches maximum depths (~1000 m) towards the basin's centre (IGME, 2009). The connection among permeable units and between both aquifer systems is complex. In some locations, it has been observed that adjacent high-porosity bodies, separated by a few tens of meters, are hydraulically disconnected. Recharge in the shallow system is due to precipitation and, in a lower proportion, to the surface drainage network and irrigation returns. The deep aquifer system replenishes from the phreatic aquifers through deep percolation and poorly constructed wells that connect both systems (Fernández Escalante, 2004). The groundwater flow in Los Arenales Aquifer is directed to the Douro River and has a predominant north-northeast direction.

In 2005, Los Arenales Aquifer was subdivided into several groundwater bodies following the WFD requirements. These groundwater bodies are groundwater management regions that facilitate assessing and managing groundwater resources. Their borders can obey factors beyond hydrogeology (CHD, 2007). We focus on Los Arenales (LA) (2398 km²) and Medina del Campo (MC) (3707 km²) groundwater bodies, which are part of Los Arenales Aquifer (7700 km²) (Fig. 1) and extend predominantly over the Avila, Segovia, and Valladolid provinces. The differentiation of LA and MC as two separate groundwater bodies is mostly administrative. In fact, no authors have pointed out significant hydrogeological differences between them.

There are three large-scale MAR sites in LA, namely Santiuste, El Carracillo, and Pedrajas-Alcazarén (Fig. 1). They extend over large areas through channels, infiltration basins, and artificial wetlands that recharge the shallow aquifer system (MARSOL, 2015). Some tests have been conducted to implement MAR in MC (Douglas et al., 2019). However, the MAR system is not operative and is therefore not considered in the present study. The main objective of MAR in LA is to reverse groundwater depletion and ensure local irrigation needs. Santiuste and El Carracillo recharge river water surpluses during winter, while Alcazarén-Pedrajas recharges reclaimed water and rooftop runoff throughout the year (Fernández-Escalante et al., 2016). The average annual volume of MAR in LA is ~5 Mm³. More details of the MAR systems are available in the report by Fernández-Escalante et al. (2016).

2.2. Theoretical background

2.2.1. Mann-Kendall test

The Mann-Kendall (MK) test (Kendall, 1970; Mann, 1945) is a

rank-based nonparametric test that assesses the significance of a time series trend (Helsel and Hirsch, 2002). The MK test has the advantage that it is not restricted to any data distribution, is less sensitive to outliers (Hamed, 2008) and is invariant when using power transformations (e.g., logarithms and squares) (Helsel and Frans, 2006).

When conducting a MK test, typically, the null hypothesis (H_0) is that the data sample is independent and identically distributed. The alternative hypothesis (H_1) is that the data sample has a monotonic trend (Yue et al., 2002).

The S statistic of the MK test, also known as Kendall's S , is provided in expression (1).

$$S = \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^n \text{sgn}(x_j - x_i) \tag{1}$$

where n is the sample size, sgn is the signal function (2), and x_i and x_j are the data samples i and j , respectively.

$$\text{sgn}(\theta) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \theta > 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } \theta = 0 \\ -1 & \text{if } \theta < 0 \end{cases} \tag{2}$$

Mann (1945) and Kendall (1970) have shown that when $n \geq 8$, the Kendall's S have an approximately normal distribution with mean and variance given in (3) and (4), respectively:

$$E(S) = 0 \tag{3}$$

$$V(S) = \frac{n(n-1)(2n+5) - \sum_{i=1}^n t_i(i-1)(2i+5)}{18} \tag{4}$$

where $E(S)$ is the expected value of S , $V(S)$ is the variance of S , and t_i is the number of ties of extent i . A standardised test statistic Z can be calculated as follows (5):

$$Z = \begin{cases} \frac{S-1}{\sqrt{V(S)}} & S > 0 \\ 0 & S = 0 \\ \frac{S+1}{\sqrt{V(S)}} & S < 0 \end{cases} \tag{5}$$

The standardised MK Z statistic fits a standard normal distribution with a mean of zero and a standard deviation of one (Yue et al., 2002).

Fig. 1. Site map illustrating the location of groundwater bodies, meteorological stations, groundwater monitoring sites, and MAR systems. LA: Los Arenales groundwater body; MC: Medina del Campo groundwater body. The coordinates are in the WGS 84 coordinate reference system (EPGS: 4326).

2.2.2. Serial autocorrelation and pre-whitening

One crucial aspect of the MK test is that it works best on autocorrelation-free time series (Helsel and Hirsch, 2002). Von Storch (1999) and Yue et al. (2002) have shown that when testing a linear trend on a series with positive autocorrelation, there is a higher probability of rejecting the null hypothesis when it is true (type I error). On the other hand, negative autocorrelated time series can result in fewer rejections of the null hypothesis when it is false (type II error). The probability of these errors is reduced through pre-whitening, which implies diminishing the serial autocorrelation before performing the MK test (Hamed, 2008). A relevant example of pre-whitening is the trend-free pre-whitening procedure (TFPW) by Yue et al. (2002), which involves removing the AR (1) component from the original time series to reduce the absolute value of the autocorrelation.

2.2.3. Theil-Sen estimator

The Theil-Sen estimator (Sen, 1968; Theil, 1992) is a slope estimator commonly employed in hydrological trend analysis. It consists of the median of the slope through all pairs of points in the data sample (6).

$$b = \text{median} \left(\frac{Y_j - Y_i}{X_j - X_i} \right) \forall j > i \quad (6)$$

X and Y are independent variables (e.g. time) and dependent variables (e.g. groundwater level), respectively.

2.2.4. Field significance

Field significance refers to the significance of regional behaviour and can be derived from local statistical tests (Douglas et al., 2000; Renard et al., 2008; Thomas and Famiglietti, 2015). Regional trends in groundwater levels can be estimated using field significance methods. One of such methods is the Regional Kendall test (Helsel and Frans, 2006), which is adequate to use when local groundwater level time series are not spatially cross-correlated. In this test, the values of local Kendall's S are added, resulting in a regional Kendall's S (7)

$$S_r = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^m S_i} \quad (7)$$

S_r is the regional Kendall's S , m is the number of observation sites (e.g., wells), and S_i is the Kendall's S of the i th observation site. The variance of the regional Kendall's S is computed utilising expression (8)

$$V(S_r) = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^m (n_i/18)(n_i - 1)(2n_i + 5)} \quad (8)$$

The distribution of S_r can also be approximated quite well by a normal curve when $m > 25$ (Helsel and Frans, 2006), and the Z statistic can be estimated using Equation (5), where S and $V(S)$ are substituted for S_r and $V(S_r)$.

When cross-correlation is present in the groundwater level time series, the local hypotheses are not independent, and the Regional Kendall test is invalid. An alternative in these cases is the empirical approach by Douglas et al. (2000), which uses the bootstrapping method (Efron, 1979) to obtain Kendall's S samples with replacement. The size of each sample equals the size of the original dataset (i.e., n), and the sampled S values correspond to those computed at each location. Subsequently, an average Kendall's S is calculated following expression (9).

$$S_a = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n S_i}{n} \quad (9)$$

where S_a is the average Kendall's S , and S_i is Kendall's S at the i th location. This procedure is repeated N times, and the empirical distribution of the probability of non-exceedance of S_a is found by ranking the obtained values of S_a through a Weibull function (10).

$$P(S_a < s) = \frac{r}{N + 1} \quad (10)$$

where P is the probability of non-exceedance, and r is the rank.

2.3. Approach

We analysed groundwater level trends on local and regional scales and average regional groundwater levels to explore whether groundwater storage in Los Arenales Aquifer has recovered over time. These analyses also allowed us to assess spatially and temporally the potential contribution of the MAR systems to the observed groundwater behaviour. We also evaluated changes in land use, agricultural water demand as a function of crop groups, the contribution of different irrigation methods, and water management measures to assess their effect on aquifer groundwater storage.

2.3.1. Local groundwater level trends

We performed the MK test for linear trend analysis in LA and MC with a significance level of 0.05 ($|Z| \geq 1.96$ considering that the test is two-tailed). First, we pre-whitened the observations utilising the TFPW method. Subsequently, we applied the original MK test to the resulting time series. However, in cases in which groundwater monitoring sites had a considerable number of observations (>50) and the slope magnitude was large enough (>0.0005), we applied the MK test without performing any pre-whitening (Yue and Wang, 2002). We considered only groundwater monitoring sites with at least five years of continuous groundwater level records, given the substantial interannual climatic variability in the region (González-Hidalgo et al., 2010). This filtering criterion reduced the number of appropriate groundwater monitoring sites to 35 in LA and 58 in MC (57% and 60% of the original number of groundwater monitoring sites, respectively). Minor gaps (≤ 2 records) in the time series were filled using linear interpolation (Wendt et al., 2020). In some groundwater level time series, linear interpolation was also used to resample groundwater levels to have a consistent time interval between contiguous observations. The slope magnitudes were computed on pre-whitened time series through the Theil-Sen estimator.

We obtained groundwater level observations from the public database of the Duero Hydrographic Confederation (CHD), which currently has 61 groundwater monitoring sites in LA and 97 in MC (Fig. 1). The available groundwater level observations span from 1985 to 2020, with a measurement frequency that changes over time. Based on that frequency, we subdivided the data and the trend analysis into three periods that coincide with significant changes concerning the MAR sites: i) period 1985–2001, which has a biannual measuring frequency and represents the situation before the implementation of MAR; ii) period 2002–2011, which features monthly groundwater level observations and entails the official inauguration of Santiuste (2002) and EL Carracillo (2003) MAR sites; iii) period 2012–2020, which has a bimonthly measuring rate and involves the start of MAR in the Pedrajas-Alcazarén MAR site (2012). Visual examples of some of the groundwater level time series from LA and MC and their corresponding trends are provided by Henao Casas et al. (2022).

Considering a single period between 2002 and 2020 was tempting to assess trends after MAR. However, we split this interval into two since the MK test requires a consistent sampling frequency, preliminary tests showed a change in the sign of some trends between the second and third periods considered (i.e., 2002–2011 and 2012–2020), and there are data gaps of up to a year in many groundwater monitoring sites between 2011 and 2013.

2.3.2. Regional groundwater level trends

The groundwater observation sites in the study area have a minor degree of cross-correlation as a result of the high heterogeneity of the aquifer. However, cross-correlation cannot be conclusively ruled out. Therefore, we assessed regional groundwater level trends through the field significance methods of the Regional Kendall test and the empirical approach by Douglas et al. (2000).

We applied the two procedures to local trends in LA, MC, and both groundwater bodies (LA + MC), considering a significance level of 0.05 ($|Z| \geq 1.96$ since the test is two-tailed). In the approach by Douglas et al. (2000), we computed the empirical distribution of the probability of non-exceedance by repeating the bootstrap method 10,000 times ($N = 10,000$).

2.3.3. Average regional groundwater level

We estimate the annual average groundwater levels for LA and MC using available groundwater level observations. We considered only groundwater monitoring sites with continuous observations between 1985 and 2001 and between 2002 and 2022 to avoid artificial values in the constructed average groundwater levels caused by the introduction of new data in between intervals. The average groundwater levels obtained were graphically compared with annual precipitation and MAR volumes.

We obtained precipitation data from two main sources. Between 1985 and 2002, the main source of daily rainfall records was the Spanish Meteorological Agency (AEMET) stations, with data spanning, in some cases, nearly 100 years. Between 2002 and 2020, we used daily precipitation data from the AEMET and InfoRiego stations at the site (Fig. 1). We summed daily precipitation values to obtain annual precipitation. For each of the three analysis periods, we constructed Thiessen polygons (Thiessen, 1911) with the available data in the area comprised of LA and MC and constructed a single time series of annual precipitation.

We added MAR volumes from the MAR sites to get a single time series. MAR volumes from Santiuste, El Carracillo, and Pedrajas-Alcazarén were provided by the Santiuste Irrigation Community, El Carracillo Irrigation Community, and the Pedrajas wastewater treatment plant. We recalculated volumes from hydrological years to calendar years based on precipitation percentages. There are uncertainties in the exact MAR volumes of two years. In 2002, there was some MAR as part of the system testing. However, the exact infiltrated volume is unknown. In 2005, the water metering device in the Santiuste water conveyance pipe broke and the reported infiltrated volume (1.3 Mm^3) was lower than the actual one.

2.3.4. Land use and irrigation methods

Land use was analysed at general and detailed levels. At the general level, we checked changes in major land use categories, namely artificial surfaces, agriculture, forest and semi-natural areas, wetlands, and water bodies. At the detailed level, we evaluated changes in irrigated agricultural land. Land use changes between 2005 and 2014 were evaluated through the Spanish Land Occupation Information System (SIOSE) inventory, available in 2005, 2009, 2011, and 2014 (SIOSE, 2022). Changes between 1990 and 2006 were explored through CORINE Land Cover, which in the above period has data for 1990, 2000 and 2006. CORINE Land Cover is a land cover inventory based on satellite images (CLC, 2022). We analysed irrigated land in terms of irrigation methods in Castile and Leon and the provinces of Avila, Segovia, and Valladolid between 2002 and 2018 using data from the Crop Area and Yield Survey (ESYRCE) of the Ministry of Agriculture, Fishery and Food (MAPA, 2021). We explored three primary irrigation methods, namely gravity, aspersion (including fixed and moving sprinklers), and localised irrigation (including dripping irrigation).

2.3.5. Agricultural water demand

We estimated the annual agricultural water demand for each groundwater body. The objective was to explore the possible impacts of different crop groups on water use. We calculated the total irrigated land for each crop group in LA by adding the contribution of municipalities located within this groundwater body. We obtained the required data from the Agricultural Statistics of the Castile and Leon Board (Junta de Castilla y León, 2022), including information for more than 70 crops comprehended in six crop groups, namely cereals, industrial crops,

fodder crops, legumes, vegetables, and tubers. Data were available between 2010 and 2020. We performed the same procedure for MC. Subsequently, we estimated the average irrigation volumes applied to each crop group using data on the water use per hectare for 17 crops in the Adaja River Irrigation District and El Carracillo. We obtained this water use information from the InfoRiego Crop Monitoring Program (InfoRiego, 2020), available between 2011 and 2018. We multiplied the total land surface of each crop group by its corresponding average irrigation volumes. Finally, crop group irrigation volumes were added to estimate annual agricultural water demand. We compared our estimate of annual agricultural water demand with the CHD assessment, which is available in the 2015–2022 Douro River basin management plan and its revision reports (CHD, 2021, 2020, 2019, 2018b, 2017, 2015).

3. Results

3.1. Local groundwater level trends

The application of the TFPW method effectively reduced the autocorrelation of the groundwater level time series by around 30% on average.

Most groundwater level trends (~100%) in the period 1985–2001 were significantly negative (Fig. 2, a, and b), attesting to a rapid decrease in groundwater storage in Los Arenales Aquifer. This decrease occurred at average rates of -1.5 m/year in LA and -0.6 m/year in MC (Fig. 3). In the following period, 2002–2011, significant trends decreased in terms of the number of groundwater monitoring sites tested (75% in LA and 60% in MC). The resulting significant trends are evenly distributed between increasing and decreasing (Fig. 2, c, and d), and the slope magnitudes are nearly 0 m/year on average (Fig. 3). Positive trends in LA are in the vicinity of the Santiuste and Pedrajas-Alcazarén MAR sites. The positive trends with small slopes found in MC (Fig. 2, c) are possibly the result of changing crop types since the main water source for irrigation remained groundwater, and no significant changes in land use were detected.

The final period, 2012–2020, is characterised by a lower proportion of significant trends (around 50% of all groundwater monitoring sites tested) and a contrasting behaviour between LA and MC. In LA, roughly three-quarters of the detected trends are positive, while the opposite is true in MC (Fig. 2, c). The magnitude of negative trends is more prominent in MC, with an average value of -0.5 m/y (Fig. 4). Such trends cluster to the west (Fig. 3, c), where large volumes of groundwater are abstracted for irrigation. In LA, positive trends can be observed in the vicinity of Pedrajas-Alcazarén and Santiuste MAR sites (Fig. 3, c). In both cases, the trends are probably the result of MAR and some irrigation returns derived from the Cega River.

Trends in the surroundings of the Adaja River Irrigation District changed from significantly negative in 2002–2011 to significantly positive in 2012–2020. This transformation is the result of shifting groundwater to surface water (through El Castro de Las Cogotas Dam) as the main irrigation water source in 2010 (Borowiecka et al., 2019; Naroua et al., 2014).

3.2. Regional groundwater level trends

No field significance was detected in any studied regions by the empirical method of Douglas et al. (2000) (Table 1), presumably due to the disparity in trend signs and the lower proportion of significant local trends regarding the number of analysed groundwater monitoring sites. The regional Kendall-test was not computed for the periods 1985–2001 and 2002–2011, since the number of available time series was below the minimum required by the method (i.e. 26). In the period 2012–2020, the Regional Kendall test results in a positive regional groundwater level trend in LA and a negative regional trend in MC (Table 1), supporting a regional recovery of groundwater levels in the former groundwater body and further deterioration of subsurface water resources in the latter. In

Fig. 2. The significance of groundwater trends in Los Arenales (LA) and Medina del Campo (MC) groundwater bodies in terms of the Z statistic (a, c, and f) and the number of increasing and decreasing trends (b, d, and g). The size of the circles spatially represents trend magnitudes through the Theil-Sen estimator. In figures a, c, and f, significant trends are those in which $|Z| \geq 1.96$ (i.e., dark red and green). Figures correspond to the analysis periods as follows: 1985–2001, a and b; 2002–2011, c and d; 2012–2020, f and g. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 3. Boxplot of trend slopes from significant groundwater level trends in Los Arenales (LA) and Medina del Campo (MC) groundwater bodies.

the same period, no field significance was detected for the region that comprises LA and MC, likely as a consequence of opposing trends at monitoring sites.

3.3. Average regional groundwater level

Average groundwater levels attest to the storage decline perceived in the region between 1985 and 2001. The decline is more pronounced in LA (-1.1 m/year) than in MC (-0.8 m/year), where groundwater levels seem to stabilise between 1995 and 2001, since rainfall in these years is above average (Fig. 4). In LA, groundwater levels start to increase at some point between 2001 and 2004 and remain in a recovery trend of 0.4 m/year. In MC, there is also a recovery in groundwater levels between 2004 and 2013, followed by a steep fall and a decreasing trend (Fig. 4). However, in MC, it seems possible that a decreasing trend started as early as 2008 and that the level computed for 2013 is out of the trend and due to high precipitation and low agricultural water

demand (Fig. 7, c). The slope of the average groundwater level in MC between 2004 and 2020 is -0.6 m/year. In both groundwater bodies, there seems to be a significant correlation between groundwater levels and precipitation (Fig. 4). In years with considerably low precipitation, such as 2017, groundwater levels also show a decline, reflecting the high dependence of Los Arenales Aquifer on precipitation despite the high anthropisation in the region.

Intentional recharge volumes correlate positively with precipitation (Fig. 4). The implementation of MAR corresponds to the start of the increasing trend in LA.

3.4. Land use

Agricultural land remained constant in LA ($\sim 53\%$ or ~ 1250 km²) and MC ($\sim 86\%$ or ~ 3150 km²) between 1990 and 2014 (Fig. 5). There are differences in absolute (100 km²) and percentage (5–7% in terms of total agricultural land use, and up to 128% percentage difference in irrigated land in MC) values between CORINE Land Cover and SIOSE due to the different approaches these programs utilise to categorise land use. Irrigation increased at varying rates in both groundwater bodies between 1990 and 2014. In the period 1990–2000, there was a notable increase of 128% of irrigated land in MC and a more discrete increase of 14% in LA (Fig. 5). From 2000 on, irrigated land increased by minor percentages (1–4%), except between 2011 and 2014, when it expanded by 29% in LA relative to 2005 (Fig. 5).

Between 2002 and 2018, sprinklers remained the most common irrigation method in Avila, Segovia, and Valladolid (i.e. the provinces that comprise the majority of LA and MC), employed in 88% of the irrigated land (1115 km²). In this region, the adoption of localised irrigation, which is the most water-efficient method, was discrete in terms of the total irrigated area in Avila, Segovia, and Valladolid, passing from 2% (24 km²) in 2002 to 14% (199 km²) in 2018 (Fig. 6, a). In Castile and Leon, irrigation modernisation had a greater impact between 2002 and 2018. The adoption of gravity methods decreased (-47% , -1104 km²) in favour of sprinkler ($+47\%$, $+974$ km²) and

Fig. 4. Average annual groundwater level in Los Arenales (LA) and Medina del Campo (MC) groundwater bodies. Annual precipitation and managed aquifer recharge volumes are included in the background as grey and blue columns. Question marks represent the uncertainties in managed aquifer recharge volumes discussed in the section on the average regional groundwater level of the approach. The analysis periods considered in the trend tests are shown through orange shades in the background. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Table 1

The Field significance of trend tests for Los Arenales (LA) and Medina del Campo groundwater bodies (MC), and both (LA + MC). Field significance was estimated using the Regional Kendall test (RK test) and the empirical method by Douglas et al. (2000) (EM). N represents the number of groundwater monitoring sites involved. Note that field significance occurs when values are below the confidence interval threshold, that is, 0.025 for a two-tailed test.

	1985–2001			2002–2011			2012–2020		
	RK test	EM	N	RK test	EM	N	RK test	EM	N
LA	–	0.37	–	–	0.50	8	1.9E-48	0.49	35
MC	–	0.50	–	–	0.50	15	1.1E-21	0.50	50
LA + MC	–	0.49	–	–	0.49	23	0.22	0.50	85

localised irrigation (+368%, +253 km²) (Fig. 6, b).

3.5. Agricultural water demand

In 2018, the most extended crop group in LA and MC was cereals, present in more than 50% of the land (Fig. 7, a). The crops in this group, such as wheat and barley, consume the lowest water volumes (Fig. 7, a). In the same year, vegetables, and tubers, which consume the most water on average, had an important extension in LA, i.e., 20% and 11%, respectively (Fig. 5, a).

The extension of some crop groups shows high interannual variation and, in some cases, trends. Between 2010 and 2018, the extension of vegetable crops in LA, which require substantial amounts of water, has encroached. On the contrary, less water intensive crops, such as cereals, were progressively more adopted. In MC, the trend is the opposite. The land extension under fodder and vegetable crops, which require more water than cereals, increased between 2010 and 2018. At the same time, agricultural land with cereal crops decreased. However, the increased adoption of industrial crops and legumes in LA, and the decrease in the extension of legumes in MC compensate for the above effect and result in nearly constant agricultural water demand for irrigation (on average, 86 Mm³/year in LA and 225 Mm³/year in MC) between 2010 and 2020 (Fig. 7, b).

At least between 2009 and 2015, the CHD calculated agricultural groundwater demands based on the irrigation groundwater rights allocated on the ALBERCA system, which is probably why our estimations differ on an annual time scale. The difference in the average between both estimates is exceedingly small for MC (2%) and large for LA (30%). The cause of the significant difference in the latter groundwater body is likely that we include in our calculation land that is being irrigated with surface water in the Adaja River Irrigation District. The same error occurs in MC, but the Adaja River Irrigation District has a smaller share of the land in this groundwater body.

Fig. 8 is a qualitative assessment of the results of the analysis conducted. The qualitative assessment is made for each analysis period and groundwater body and consists of assigning a category out of four possible indicating the actual or likely impact on groundwater storage:

Fig. 5. Total agricultural land use and irrigated agricultural land in Los Arenales (LA) and Medina del Campo groundwater bodies through a) CORINE Land Cover information between 1990 and 2006 and b) SIOSE between 2005 and 2014. Total agricultural land use is represented as a percentage of the total area. Irrigated agricultural land is expressed as a percentage change relative to the initial value in 1990 (a) and 2005 (b).

Fig. 6. Irrigated land as a function of the irrigation method: a) Provinces of Avila, Segovia, and Valladolid. b) Castile and Leon.

Fig. 7. Analysis related to agricultural water demand: a) crop group distribution in Los Arenales (LA) and Medina del Campo (MC) groundwater bodies in 2018 and average irrigation volume; b) agricultural water demand estimated in the present study and by the CHD.

increasing, decreasing, neutral, and not assessed. We considered designating the “increasing” category for the analyses involving groundwater levels when the results indicate an increase in this variable. In the case of land use, we assumed that increasing the area under irrigation (we selected 5% as a threshold) can result in higher abstractions and, thus, a decrease in storage (“decreasing” category). Concerning the irrigation method, wider adoption of technologies that save water (sprinkler and drip irrigation) would likely decrease abstractions and thus indicate an increase (“increasing” category) in groundwater storage. The opposite categories are assigned when groundwater water levels decline, irrigated land decreases, or the use of the less water efficient technologies increases.

Fig. 8 shows that the main difference between LA and occurs in the last period (2012–2020), when positive slopes and increasing trends at the regional and local levels imply an increase in groundwater storage in LA and a decrease in MC. This qualitative analysis also shows that, in our case, the agricultural water demand has, to the depth of our analysis, a limited impact on water resources and very likely on groundwater storage.

4. Discussion

In this section, first, we integrate and discuss the results for each analysis period. Subsequently, we elaborate on the effect of MAR on the study area and provide a brief outlook.

4.1. Period 1985–2000

The analyses conducted reflect the dramatic decrease in groundwater storage in the area in the last quarter of the XX century. Significant groundwater level trends and the slope of those trends were significantly negative in both groundwater bodies (Fig. 2a and b, and Fig. 3). Furthermore, the average groundwater level also reflected the decrease in storage. This observed deterioration of groundwater resources in Los Arenales Aquifer was probably the result of three main factors: i) the lack of regulation of water use: the Spanish 29/1985 Water Act of 1985 proclaimed groundwater a public good, resulting in the need to formalise a considerable number of previous private rights and granting new concessions. These tasks overflowed the institutional capacity of local authorities, which could not manage requests in time, giving a

Groundwater body		Method	1985-2001	2002-2011	2012-2020
LA	Local GWL trends		Decreasing	Neutral	Increasing
	GWL Slopes		Decreasing	Neutral	Increasing
	Regional GWL trends		Not assessed	Not assessed	Increasing
	Average regional GWL		Decreasing	Increasing	Increasing
	Land use		Decreasing	Neutral	Decreasing
	Irrigation method		Not assessed	Increasing	Increasing
	Agricultural water demand		Not assessed	Neutral	Neutral
MC	Local GWL trends		Decreasing	Neutral	Decreasing
	GWL Slopes		Decreasing	Neutral	Decreasing
	Regional GWL trends		Not assessed	Not assessed	Decreasing
	Average regional GWL		Decreasing	Increasing	Decreasing
	Land use		Decreasing	Neutral	Decreasing
	Irrigation method		Not assessed	Increasing	Increasing
	Agricultural water demand		Not assessed	Neutral	Neutral

Impact on groundwater storage

 Increasing	 Neutral
 Decreasing	 Not assessed

Fig. 8. Qualitative summary of the different methods explored. GWL: groundwater level; LA: Los Arenales groundwater body; MC: Medina del Campo groundwater body.

sense of impunity to illegal drilling (Martínez-Santos et al., 2008). Furthermore, under the 29/1985 Water Act (developed in the Regulation of the Public Hydraulic Domain, Royal Decree 849/1986), permits were not required to drill wells with small abstraction volumes (7000 m³/year) (Llamas and Garrido, 2007). The Groundwater Register and Catalogue Update Program (ARYCA) (1995–2001), which aimed to improve water use tracking and control, felt short in its objectives and did not provide a significant solution to illegal and unregistered groundwater abstractions (Llamas et al., 2015); ii) the incentivisation of highly water consumptive crops (e.g., sugar beet and maize) via the European Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) subsidies between 1986 and 1992 (Baraja Rodríguez, 2012; Martínez-Santos et al., 2008): although no crop distribution information is available for this period, exploration of Corina Land Cover reveals an increase in irrigated land, which was particularly high in MC (+136% between 1990 and 2000) (Fig. 5, a) and probably boosted by the incentives above; and iii) the occurrence of three major droughts in the Douro River basin (i.e. 1989-1990, 1991–1996, and 2001–2002) (CHD, 2018a; Del Pozo Garrido et al., 2006) which reflect in below-average precipitation in Fig. 4, and resulted in water scarcity in the region.

4.2. Period 2000–2011

During this period, average groundwater levels in LA and MC show a moderate increase (Fig. 4). At the same time, groundwater level trends at monitoring sites are evenly distributed between increasing and decreasing (Fig. 2, c, and d), resulting in average trend slopes of approximately 0 m/year (Fig. 3). We believe that the observed patterns are predominantly a consequence of a rebound effect on groundwater levels caused by the progressive increase in precipitation between 2004 and 2008 and restrictions on water use (particularly during the 2004–2005 drought, as reported by the CHD (2018a), additional recharge due to MAR (see the location of increasing trends in LA, Fig. 2, c), more control on water resources due to the creation of irrigation communities, and stabilisation in the extension of irrigated land (Fig. 4a and b). The information explored also reflects a relatively small impact of irrigation modernisation in the provinces comprising LA and MC (i.e. Avila, Segovia, and Valladolid) in comparison to the autonomous

community of Castile and Leon (Fig. 7), which witnessed a greater adoption of sprinkler and localised irrigation, two methods that imply a lower water loss to evaporation than gravity irrigation (Corominas Masip and Cuevas Navas, 2017). Some of the programs that promoted changes in irrigation methods include the National Irrigation Plan - Horizon 2008 (enacted in 2002), the Irrigation Modernisation Shock Plan 2006–2008, and the Strategy for the Sustainable Modernisation of Irrigation 2010–2015 (Gómez-Espín, 2019; Lopez-Gunn et al., 2012). The ALBERCA project, a successor to ARYCA, has also been unable to track groundwater use comprehensively and effectively (Llamas et al., 2015). A recent study by Bea Martínez et al. (2021) has shown that illegal groundwater abstractions in Los Arenales represent at least 30% of legally allocated rights. Droughts in 2004–2005 and 2011–2013 that occurred in the Douro River basin affected both groundwater bodies. However, groundwater levels recovered quickly in the following years (Fig. 4).

4.3. Period 2012–2020

In LA, groundwater levels continue to recover (Fig. 4). Most trends increase (Fig. 2, f, and g) and have a positive average slope (Fig. 3). Furthermore, there is positive field significance (Table 1). In MC, conditions deteriorate. More than a fourth of the trends are decreasing (Fig. 2 f and g), and field significance and the average slope are negative (Fig. 3 and Table 1).

The primary cause of the observed deterioration of MC is low precipitation, which resulted in droughts in 2011–2013 and 2016–2018 (CHD, 2018a; Del Pozo Garrido et al., 2006). The improved groundwater storage observed in LA is probably a result of MAR. This conclusion is supported by the spatial correlation of positive trends (Fig. 2, f, and g) and the fact that this is the only water management measure in which LA and MC differ. The contribution of other water management measurements, including the implementation of new irrigation modernisation programmes at the national level (i.e. The National Irrigation Plan, 2014–2020 and 2018–2025), has a limited impact on the provinces that comprise LA and MC (Fig. 6, a) compared to Castile and Leon. However, this measure could have a net positive and significant impact on Los Arenales Aquifer. The contrary is also possible. In some parts of Spain,

farmers use the water saved through irrigation modernisation to expand irrigated land or change to more water intensive crops (Berbel et al., 2019; Lecina et al., 2010; Lopez-Gunn et al., 2012). The impact of irrigation modernisation requires further analyses that involve detailed information on agricultural practices and water use.

4.4. Managed aquifer recharge and outlook

We consider MAR to be the water management measure responsible for improving groundwater quantity in LA. There is a spatial and temporal correlation between MAR and increasing groundwater level trends in LA. Our results align with the analysis by Henao Casas et al., 2022, showing the adequacy of this technology to cope with drought, which is especially visible in the groundwater level analyses of the last period (2012–2020). Water management measures implemented on a national and regional scale, including plans for the modernisation of irrigation, and programs to quantify groundwater abstractions (e.g., ALBERCA), have had a limited impact on the study area, at least to the depth of our analysis. Irrigated land has expanded at different rates since 1985, and there is no systematic change in crop types that could result in tangible groundwater savings. MC probably represents how the situation would be in LA if MAR was not implemented.

About 32% of the irrigated land in LA is located in areas that benefit from MAR. The average annual recharge from MAR ($\sim 5 \text{ Mm}^3$) is about 25% of the irrigation demands in the areas with MAR, and 8% of the average agricultural groundwater demand in LA (61 Mm^3). The effect of additional water resources is greatly enhanced by establishing irrigation communities, which gather farmers who exploit the resources from MAR. These communities, which have been formed in Santiuste and El Carracillo, have contributed to more effective control of water demand. They have become a platform to connect farmers and the CHD, contributing to negotiating water rights, installing water metering devices in abstraction wells, and transferring knowledge to face dry years and use water efficiently, among other benefits (Fernández Escalante and López Gunn et al., 2021; Giordano et al., 2021; Lopez-Gunn, 2003). Evidence of cooperation between the CHD and irrigation communities has been found beyond stakeholder workshops conducted in the past (Fernández-Escalante et al., 2016). For example, the CHD has requested farmers in irrigation communities irrigate only 50% of their plots and obtain one harvest per year (FNCA, 2020). According to SIOSE, in 2014, approximately 35% of the irrigated land in LA was not being irrigated, contrasting with only 15% in MC.

Despite the tangible improvement in groundwater storage, there are still challenges in LA and especially MC that warrant further governance and infrastructure efforts. Both groundwater bodies are still considered in a bad quality and quantity status as per the WFD and in bad quantitative condition according to the groundwater exploitation index (groundwater usage over available resources), which in 2018 was 0.92 and 1.57 for LA and MC, respectively (CHD, 2019). A good quantitative status is considered when the groundwater exploitation index is below 0.8 (Ministerio de Medio Ambiente y Medio Rural y Marino, 2008). In addition, climate change in the Douro River basin is likely to have a detrimental impact on natural recharge through less rainfall, lower streamflow, and higher temperatures (Amblar Francés et al., 2017; Cruz-García et al., 2016; Guerreiro et al., 2017; Guerreiro et al., 2016). Climate change could further affect Los Arenales Aquifer due to the reliability and flexibility of groundwater when dealing with water scarcity (Famiglietti, 2014; Hanjra and Qureshi, 2010).

5. Conclusions

This study has shown that managed aquifer recharge (MAR) has contributed to reversing the consequences of intensive groundwater use and sustaining irrigation in Los Arenales groundwater body (LA). Groundwater level trends show a significant decrease in LA and Medina del Campo groundwater bodies (MC) between 1985 and 2001, with

slope magnitudes of around -1.5 m/year and -0.6 m/year , respectively, and negative trends at almost 100% of groundwater monitoring sites. The subsequent period, 2002–2011, is characterised by positive and negative trends in equal proportions in LA and MC and slopes averaging $\sim 0 \text{ m/year}$. The final period shows a better situation in LA, where trends are predominantly positive ($\sim 75\%$) and spatially related to MAR. The average slope is slightly above zero (i.e., 0.2 m/year). On the other hand, MC has predominantly negative trends ($\sim 75\%$) and a negative mean slope of approximately -0.5 m/year .

No field significance was found through the empirical method by Douglas et al. (2000). A significant regional positive trend was found through the Regional Kendall test in LA and a negative trend in MC between 2012 and 2020.

Agricultural land use remained stable between 1985 and 2020. In the same period, irrigated land has increased throughout the region. The distribution of the major crop groups has changed over time, but agricultural water demand has remained virtually constant since at least 2010. The effect of water management measures and programs, such as a comprehensive database to track groundwater use and modernisation of irrigation, is limited on the study area.

Average groundwater levels show that LA has entered a recovery trend between 2001 and 2004, coinciding with the start of MAR. The difference in groundwater level trends observed in LA and MC is due to the implementation of MAR in the former groundwater body.

Author contributions:

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Funding

The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement no 814066 (Managed Aquifer Recharge Solutions Training Network - MARSOLU).

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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